

RDA Minimal MD Set Comparison
As of RDA Plenary 17, April 2021

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	RDA Minimal MD Set (See Legend below)					
2		1	2	3		
3		Barker- FAIRsFAIR consultancy	EOSC WG Training&Skills	Garcia et al PLoS Paper	Definitions for Garcia set	Notes for RDA Minimal set
4	Title	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1007854	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/1007854	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007854		
5	Keywords					
6	Description	Title	Title	Title		
7	Author	Keywords	Keywords	Keyword	Keywords or tags identifying the topic of the materials	
8	Licence	Description	Description	Description	Overview of the subject matter, aims of the training and language in which the training is delivered	
9		Author	Author	Contact details	Author(s) name and contact details	Author as person or organization
10	Modification date	Licence	Licence	Licensing and reuse details	License and rules and conditions for (re)use and contribution	
11	<i>Primary Language</i>	Learning outcome	Learning outcome	Learning outcomes	Statements that indicate what trainees should be able to do upon successful completion	
12	URL		Date modified	Date of last revision	Date of last update of the materials and the version	
13	Locator Type		<i>Language</i>			
14	Target audience	Location	URL			To LR or its landing page; equivalent to "location"; "should be a PID", if possible.
15	Skill level					Provides explanation of name space or catalog for URL above, e.g., DOI, Handle, etc.
16	Subject Domain		Target group	Target audience	The intended audience, their prerequisite knowledge and skills, their general background and how the training material will help them	
17	<i>Learning Outcome</i>	Educational level	Level			
18	<i>Access cost</i>	Subject	Domain			
19	<i>Learning resource type</i>		<i>Learning objective</i>			
20	MD_record_PID		<i>Access conditions</i>			
21		<i>Learning resource type</i>				

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22						Globally unique, persistent ID for the metadata record within the system for the resource being described. Most useful for Service Provider Users. Could be a combination of the 3 terms used by ENVRI LOM or just specified to include as part of this PID. Would not be included in the minimal set for learners & trainers, but should be documented as necessary assumption for the discovery of all users and with specific explanations of necessity for service provider, and developer user stories.
23			PID			
24		Publisher				
25		Typical learning time				
26				Preferred citation	Instructions on how to cite	
27				Structure and duration	Description of the structure of the materials and setting in which to deliver them, including the time allocated to each part (lectures, exercises etc)	
28				Additional information	Items that provide additional guidance about (re)use and delivery of the materials (e.g. general topics and guidance)	
29				Links and references	Links and references that are relevant to the content but not required for delivery of the materials	
30				Required resources	Technical resources and related materials (software requirements, datasets, infrastructure requirements etc)	
31	Legend:					
32	Bold = common to 3 (or more) sources		Title, Description, Keywords, Author(s), Licence, Target audience, Skill level, Subject domain			
33	Italic = common to 2 sources		Learning outcome, Educational / skill level, Location (URL in EOSC WG, possibly part of 'preferred citation' in Garcia et al), Access cost/condition,			
	Grey italic= may be equivalent but not a direct mapping		Learning outcome/objective, Access cost/condition, Language (part of description in Garcia et al), Publisher (part of 'contact details' in Garcia et al?), Typical learning time ('time allocated' in Garcia et al 'structure and duration')			
34	Black, no emphasis or color: In 1 source but not in other		Learning resource type (Barker), Required resources, Additional information, Links and references (Garcia et al)			
35	NB. one 'term' may imply multiple 'fields', any of which may be populated by a controlled vocabulary					
36						